

The Role of Position and Quantum Mechanics in 1D Reflection-Refraction

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In previous notes, we argued that the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$ leads to degeneracies: $x=x_0+n\hbar/p$ and $t=t_0+n\hbar/E$ (n =integer). These, in turn, lead to spatial resolution pockets of length \hbar/p . To create a probability $P_1(px)$ such that $P_1(p_1x)P_1(p_2x)=P_1((p_1+p_2)x)$, one has $\exp(ipx)$ as a solution which neither shrinks or grows indefinitely. Physically, $\exp(ipx)$ may be applied to describe 2-slit interference-diffraction.

If one considers the problem of 1 dimensional reflection-refraction, one has an interface at a sharp point x_0 (between n_1 and n_2 , two indices of refraction). x_0 is an idealization, but suggests that the interface is quite sharp. If one writes the conservation of probability statement: $1 = P(\text{reflection}) + P(\text{refraction})$ ((1)), then spatial position does not appear anywhere in this equation. As a result, one might assume that the reflection and refraction probabilities are determined at the point x_0 . Even if one has $\exp(ip_1x)$ for an incident photon, $\exp(-ip_1x)$ for a reflected, and $\exp(ip_2x)$ for a refracted, these quantum probabilities are linked with position, while ((1)) is not. They might be considered relevant to a 2-slit apparatus at x_0 . As a result, one might consider ((1)) and the quantum probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ to be completely independent.

The problem with this viewpoint, we argue, is that the properties of the refracted beam, namely c_2 and p_2 cannot be determined at a sharp (or almost sharp) point x_0 . c_2 and p_2 are average values which must be established over a finite length into the material n_2 because this material consists of molecules and free space. As a result, the properties c_2 and p_2 which define the refracted beam occur over some length. A photon which enters the region n_2 at x_0 is not yet considered a refracted photon because its c_2 and p_2 properties have not been established. This is further demonstrated by writing ((1)) as $AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2$ where AA , BB , CC represent fluxes of the incident, reflected and refracted beams and c_1 and c_2 the speeds. c_2 again is not established until the photon spends some time in the n_2 region.

As a result, one has ((1)) which displays no x dependence while at the same time one cannot define a refracted beam until it has traversed some length in n_2 , and also the quantum $\exp(ipx)$ picture. We try to show that ((1)) cannot be independent of equations consisting of length, and these must ultimately bring in the values A, B, C . The equations exhibiting length then become independent of length when one multiplies the complex conjugate of $\exp(ipx)$ continuities with $\exp(ipx)$ first derivative continuity to reduce information and obtain ((1)).

Free Particle Quantum Mechanics From The Lorentz Invariant $A = -Et+px$

We have argued in previous notes that free particle quantum mechanics emerges from the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$ because this yields the degeneracies:

$$x=x_0 + n\hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad t=t_0 + n\hbar/E \quad n=\text{integer} \quad ((2))$$

As a result, there are temporal and spatial pockets of length \hbar/E and \hbar/p with uniform t and x probability within. If, however, one requires that:

$P_1(p_1x)P_1(p_2x) = P((p_1+p_2)x)$ where P_1 is some kind of probability function ((3))

Then: $P_1(px) = \exp(ipx)$ (and $P_1(Et) = \exp(-iEt)$) ((4))

((4)) ensures that the probability neither grows or decreases indefinitely. The probability $\exp(ipx)$ is justified experimentally in the analysis of the n-slit interference-diffraction problem. This applies to a photon as well as a particle with rest mass.

If, however, one has one dimensional reflection-refraction (photon), one might argue that $\exp(ipx)$ is suitable for describing an interaction with a 2-slit apparatus placed either in a region with index of refraction n_1 , or in the region with n_2 , but has nothing to do with the probabilities to reflect or refract ((1)). After all, $\exp(ipx)$ is about spatial resolution, not changing from one state to another.

The Case for $\exp(ipx)$ Being Applicable in 1D Reflection-Refraction

Even if one starts with the a priori assumption that ((1)) is completely independent of the reflection and refraction probabilities, one may still argue that the form $\exp(ipx)$ needs to be considered at the n_1 - n_2 interface x_0 , which is idealized as a point. $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability linked to an interaction with an n--slit apparatus (for example). The photon or particle interacts with each slit because there is a spatial resolution of the length \hbar/p . At the x_0 point, there are actually two average p values, p_1 and p_2 and both affect resolution. We suggest that a 2-slit apparatus placed at x_0 would take into consideration both $\exp(ip_1x)$ and $\exp(ip_2x)$.

As a result, there seem to be grounds for making $\exp(ipx)$ a continuous function at x_0 . One, however, should also make the first derivative d/dx continuous so one does not have a cusp. This, however, leads to issues. One is forced to introduce a third piece, namely a reflected photon and add weights to the incident, reflected and refracted $\exp(ipx)$ values. At this point, there is no reason to suggest that these weights have anything to do with $P(\text{reflection})$ and $P(\text{refraction})$. One is simply dealing with the resolution probability, $\exp(ipx)$, which is linked to interference/diffraction patterns from 2-slit interactions. The two resulting equations are:

$$A\exp(ip_1x) + B\exp(-ip_1x) = C \exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x_0 \quad ((5a))$$

$$Ap_1 \exp(ip_1x) - p_1B \exp(-ip_1x) = p_2C \exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x_0 \quad ((5b))$$

Setting $A=1$, one may solve for B and C in terms of c_1, c_2 or alternatively p_1, p_2 .

Again, at this point there is no reason to consider B and C linked to reflection and refraction probabilities.

1 = P(reflection) + P(refraction)

The probability conservation equation ((1)) does not contain any length information. In other words, it suggests that $P(\text{reflection})$ and $P(\text{refraction})$ occur exactly at x_0 , the n_1 - n_2 interface. The main point of this note is to argue that this leads to a problem. A refracted beam is defined

by its c_2 and p_2 values. These values are averages which require some length over which to be established. One cannot state that there is a reflected photon until it has traversed some length within n_2 . We argue this because n_2 consists of molecules and free space and c_2 and p_2 are the result of interactions and motion in this free space. As a result, ((1)), which shows no length, may be a little misleading. One must indeed consider length regions in the reflection-refraction problem even if one only wants information about $P(\text{reflection})$ and $P(\text{refraction})$, we argue.

We suggest that this implies that the $\exp(ipx)$ length resolution approach is also applicable to the establishment of $P(\text{reflection})$ and $P(\text{refraction})$. $A=1$, B, C cannot be independent of $P(\text{reflection})$ and $P(\text{refraction})$ and equations ((5a)) and ((5b)) must be underlying equations associated with reflection and refraction. One may next ask: Why aren't B and C the probabilities $P(\text{reflection})$ and $P(\text{refraction})$? First, one may see that for $n_1 > n_2$ and $c_i = c/n_i$, $B < 0$. Thus, B cannot be $P(\text{reflection})$. Furthermore, ((5a)) and ((5b)) make use of motion in space whereas ((1)) is simply a probability conservation equation. In other words, it contains less information. In other words, the square root probability (or wavelength) contains more information than the square W^*W . Thus, there are two sets of probabilities, one continuing more information than the other. The quantum problem is solved using the more informational (wavelength) approach. Then W^*W removes information leaving only the lesser information, $P(\text{reflection})$ and $P(\text{refraction})$ in this case, that one wants.

We suggest that one must take ((5a)) and ((5b)) and remove information such that one only keeps information about $P(\text{reflection})$ and $P(\text{refraction})$. If one uses $x_0=0$, then $\exp(ip_1 \cdot 0) = \exp(ip_2 \cdot 0) = 1$ and there is no x_0 , but if x_0 is not 0, one may multiply the complex conjugate of ((5a)) by ((5b)) to obtain a difference of squares on the LHS and CCp_2 on the RHS and eliminate x_0 . In other words, one loses information by combining the two equations, but retains the conservation of probability information in ((1)).

The main point we try to make, however, is that one must be able to justify why ((1)), which contains no length information, must actually be linked to a scenario which describes probability in space and we argue that this is because p_2 and c_2 must be established over a length in space.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the form $\exp(ipx)$ from free particle quantum mechanics is linked with probability/resolution in space and pertains to experiments such as 2-slit diffraction. One dimensional reflection-refraction at a point x_0 , however, does not seem to depend on resolutions at first glance, i.e. one has $1 = P(\text{reflection}) + P(\text{refraction})$. One might be tempted to state that $P(\text{reflection})$ and $P(\text{refraction})$ are determined at x_0 . Even if one were to place a 2-slit apparatus at x_0 and consider $\exp(ip_1 x)$ s and their first derivatives d/dx being continuous at x_0 with $\exp(ip_2 x)$ and its first derivative (and thus adding coefficients A, B, C and a reflected photon), this would have nothing to do with $P(\text{reflection})$ and $P(\text{refraction})$.

We argue, however, that a refracted photon is defined by c_2 and p_2 . These are average values which arise due to collision with molecules in n_2 and motion in free space in between molecules. Thus, the very notion of a refracted beam depends on length in n_2 and one cannot define a $P(\text{refracted})$ at x_0 . This suggests that even ((1)) must be based on a length probabilistic

treatment. We suggest that this is the $\exp(ipx)$ ((5a)) ((5b)) continuity of $\exp(ipx)$ s and their first derivatives at x_0 .

If one is then only interested in $P(\text{reflected})$ and $P(\text{refracted})$ one must remove extra length information by multiplying the complex conjugate of ((5a)) by ((5b)) to obtain $1 = P(\text{reflected}) + P(\text{refracted})$.

In other words, in quantum mechanics one has a wavefunction, $W(x)$, which contains more information than a second probability $W^*(x)W(x)$. One usually solves a problem using $W(x)$, i.e. the probability with more information. One may then remove information using $W^*(x)W(x)$ to retain lesser information such as $P(\text{reflected})$ and $P(\text{refracted})$